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Title

DiSSCo Prepare Deliverable 5.3 "DiSSCo Digital Specimen Object Specifications"

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Abstract

This is the deliverable report of the DiSSCo Prepare Deliverable 5.3 "DiSSCo Digital Specimen Object

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The first version of openDS as described here does not claim to be complete, it merely covers the most prominent use cases for openDS and is expected to grow with subsequent releases.

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DiSSCo Digital Specimen Object Specifications

DiSSCo Prepare WP 5 – Deliverable 5.3

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Abstract

This is the deliverable report of the DiSSCo Prepare Deliverable 5.3 “DiSSCo Digital Specimen Object Specifications”. It describes how the specification for the Open Digital Specimen (openDS) model was created by a combined workgroup from the DiSSCo Prepare 5.2 and 6.2, how its terms were modelled using the DiSSCo Modelling Framework (DMF), the concepts covered by its first version and how this version was exported into a JSON Schema file for data validation within the DiSSCo Technical Infrastructure and a human readable documentation.

The first version of openDS as described here does not claim to be complete, it merely covers the most prominent use cases for openDS and is expected to grow with subsequent releases.

Keywords

Distributed System of Scientific Collections, DiSSCo RI, Open Digital Specimen, openDS, DiSSCo Modelling Framework, FAIR, Digital Extended Specimen, FAIR Digital Object, Semantic Modelling, Standard Development, Structured Data

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01 Introduction

About this report

This report builds on the Deliverable Report D5.2 DiSSCo Modelling Framework (Fichtmueller & Güntsch 2022). It is assumed that the reader is familiar with the core ideas of the DMF.

This report is not a documentation of the specification itself, but a description of how the specification was created and where it is documented.

DiSSCo Modelling Framework

The DiSSCo Modelling Framework (DMF)¹ is an installation of the Wikibase suite², which consists of the Mediawiki software with a set of Wikibase extensions that allow for structured data input akin to Wikidata.

The DMF was set up to model the terms of the DiSSCo Digital Specimen Object Specifications. So far within the DMF only the data model of the Open Digital Specimen (openDS) has been defined and thus within this report we only refer to the openDS specification, though other data models might be added in the future and therefore extending the DMF beyond openDS.

As the DMF is using the Wikibase/Mediawiki software, it supports most of the features that Wikidata or Wikipedia offer. Key features of the Wikibase suite that are important for the DMF include:

- Collaborative editing with a robust versioning system
- User-friendly input of structured data
- Automated import through API access or tools like QuickStatements
- Structured querying and dynamic export through the Query Service

These features were essential for creating the openDS data model in the DMF. They also facilitated the different pipelines to export the data model and convert it for future reference into a JSON Schema. This schema can then be used for the automated processing and validation of specimen data by the DiSSCo infrastructure and to generate human readable documentation of the terms that make up openDS.

¹ <https://modelling.dissco.tech>

² <https://wikiba.se/>

02 Process

Creation Process of openDS

The work on the openDS data model was done by a joint group of the DiSSCo Tasks 5.2 and 6.2 in biweekly video conferences.

A collaborative diagram (not part of the Wikibase installation of the DMF) was used as the initial design ground where classes and their properties could easily and quickly be sketched out and changed. This allowed for faster prototyping and an easier overview than the DMF would have provided. After there was a general consensus on a class and its properties, the terms were created in the DMF and fleshed out with all the necessary details both to make them understandable for humans (adding definitions, examples or usage notes) and to describe the terms with the required flags for the automated processing and export.

Figure 1: a screenshot of the box model used to design and discuss the openDS data model within the modelling group.

Modelling of Terms in the DiSSCo Modelling Framework

The terms from the openDS data model are of three different types: Classes, Object Properties and Datatype Properties. The names for these types are taken from the world of ontological modelling, even though it was not primarily designed to be an ontology. An additional export as an ontology would enable the usage of higher logical functions like reasoning and inference which are not supported by the current schemas based on RDF graph validation (cp. Labra Gayo 2018).

Depending on the type of the term, different properties within the Wikibase (not to be confused with the properties as concept types, i.e. Object Properties and Datatype Properties) are used to describe and structure them, so that they can be suitably exported into the different target formats, such as JSON Schema or the human readable documentation.

There are some elements that describe all of the items in the DMF, regardless of whether they are classes, object properties or datatype properties.

Label	The human readable name of the item.
Description	The description or definition of the item.
Part of	Denotes that an item is part of the openDS Scheme. This allows for the development of multiple specifications within the DMF.
Is of Type	Denotes the type of an item: Class, Object Property or Datatype Property.
Concept Name	The machine readable version of the name of the item. It usually is the label without the spaces and in camel case notation.
Modified	A date stamp of the last significant edit of the term. This is used as the identifier for the versioned terms.
In Concept Group	For grouping related concepts into concept groups, e.g. Multimedia Elements. This is not relevant for the data model itself but it helps users to better understand the structure of the scheme.
Has exact match	For mapping to terms from other terminologies that have the same meaning. The mapping is done via the URI of the external term.
Has related match	For mapping to terms from other terminologies that have a related meaning. The mapping is done via the URI of the external term.
Not to be confused with	To distinguish between concepts with similar names but different meanings or types.

Classes

Classes define the different groups of objects within the Digital Specimen Specification. In the box model pictured in Fig. 1, classes are the boxes with their class names centred in the top row. The lines of text that are listed within the box of a class are its properties.

Some classes are abstract classes that are not intended to be instantiated as objects but only to give common properties to their inheriting subclasses, e.g. the class Agent is the abstract parent class for Organization, Person and MachineAgent.

Is of type	Notes if a class is a type, i.e. it will be exported into a JSON Schema file later on.
Subclass of	To denote the inheritance of a class by linking to its superclass.
contains	Lists the properties that are connected to a class. Each property listed can have additional details on its specific behaviour within the class, described using the qualifiers from the Wikibase data model.
Is mandatory	Denotes if a property is required for a class.
Is repeatable	Denotes if the same property can occur multiple times.
Export order	Although the order of the properties is not important for the data model, this allows the maintainer to define an order in which the properties should be exported for the purpose of documentation, so that they are more sensible to the human reader, by moving important properties to the top and by grouping related ones.
Section	If the current class uses sections to group their properties, this defines the section the property appears within the current class, e.g. the authoritative section for the Digital Specimen.
Example	A language independent example value for that property in the current class.
Example localized	A language dependent example value for that property in the current class with the language it is in.
Additional description	Additional or alternative description or definition of the item in the context of the current class.
Usage notes	Additional description of how a property should be used within the context of the current class.

Example, Example localized, (Additional) Description and Usage notes are usually stated within the property itself, their usage here would give specific details in the context of the current class, if generic information of the

property doesn't describe the specific situation sufficiently.

Digital Specimen (Q29)

Digital Specimen object

Language	Label	Description
English	Digital Specimen	Digital Specimen object

Statements

instance of	Type	
is part of	openDS	
contains	Identifier	
	export order	1
	is mandatory	1
	Source System ID	
	export order	2
	Physical Specimen ID	
section	primary specimen data	

Figure 2: the class for the Digital Specimen object in the DiSSCo Modelling Framework (compacted screenshot).

Properties

Properties are further distinguished between Object Properties and Datatype properties. Nevertheless, there are several descriptive elements that are used for both types:

Subproperty of	To denote the inheritance of a property by linking to its superproperty.
Is coupled with	To denote properties that co-occur with each other. If one is present, the other one is expected to be present as well, e.g. latitude and longitude for coordinates.
Expected at MIDS level	To indicate the MIDS level at which a property is expected to show up
Additional description	The field for the description within Wikibase has a technical limit on its length. If the required definition of an element needs to be longer than that, it can be put here.
Usage Notes	Additional information on how an element is supposed to be used. This is usually not as strictly defined as an element's description/definition.

Object Properties

Object properties are properties of classes that point to other classes. In the box model pictured in Fig. 1, object properties are the text lines within the boxes that have arrows pointing to other boxes.

Has range To denote the class to which an object property points to.

Datatype Properties

Datatype properties are properties of classes that have actual content. The content itself depends on the datatype of the property, such as text, integer numbers, floating point numbers, etc. In the box model pictured in Fig. 1, datatype properties are the text lines within the boxes that don't have any arrows pointing to other boxes.

Datatype To denote the datatype of a datatype property. The datatypes are usually from the XML Schema specification and described using the xs: prefix, e.g.: xs:string, xs:integer, xs:boolean, xs:dateTime

minimum To denote the lowest expected value of a numerical property.

maximum To denote the highest expected value of a numerical property.

Example A language independent example value for the property.

Example localized A language dependent example value for that property with the language it is in.

Exporting a new version of openDS

Figure 3: Exporting a new version from the DMF.

When the modelling process has reached a certain maturity for a release, there are a couple of steps required to formally create and release a new version of the specification, illustrated in Figure 3.

Versioning Tool

Each term has the modified field, which expresses the latest change to the term. All terms that have been changed since the last release can be queried by their modified date. That list of terms is then fed to the versioning tool which will duplicate the item, set it as an instance of “versioned term” and link it back to the original term using the element “mostRecentVersion”. The versioned term is then protected from further edits.

Figure 4: Schematic representation of a term, its versions and their relations (Fichtmueller & Güntsch 2022)

Documentation Export Script

After the versions of the terms have been generated, the export script can be run. It queries the DMF using the SPARQL interface and gets lists of the classes, the properties and their connections. These lists are then used to generate a human readable documentation of the terms. The script is written as a Jupyter Notebook in Python and is available at the DiSSCo Github repository³. It generates a static HTML website that contains the documentation for all of the terms.

Upload documentation to terms.dissco.tech

After the documentation has been created, it needs to be uploaded to the server that hosts the documentation. Together with the accompanying CSS files it is stored in the respective directory so that the documentation becomes publicly available at <https://terms.dissco.tech/documentation/opens/>.

Model Publishing for JSON Schema

During the creation and updating of Digital Extended Specimen instances within the DiSSCo infrastructure it will be necessary to validate incoming data regarding its compliance with the openDS model. Therefore, certain restrictions on properties are formulated in the Modelling Framework, for example the datatype of a property or whether the property’s occurrence is mandatory on a type. In

³ <https://github.com/DiSSCo/DMF-documentation-export>

order for these restrictions to be machine-readable and processable they must be transformed into a standardised format for validation. Several specifications have been developed to describe the shape of structured data, for example XML Schema Definition Language (XSD) for XML data, JSON Schema for JSON data and the Shapes Constraints Language (SHACL) or Shapes Expression Language for RDF data (ShEx, Labra Gayo 2018). Several tools and software libraries exist which implement these specifications, thus allowing data validation to be performed based on a user-defined shapes or schema definition and input to be validated. Since the principal data exchange format within the DiSSCo infrastructure will be JSON (Leeflang 2022), the most relevant of the mentioned specifications is JSON Schema. Consequently, the validation of new data based on the JSON Schema specification has been implemented in the processing service of the DiSSCo technical architecture (see Fig. 3).

In order to bridge the Modelling Framework with the other components of the technical architecture, a prototypical export script has been created. Analogously to the export script mentioned above, this script queries the SPARQL endpoint of the Modelling Framework to retrieve a structured definition of the openDS types and properties (including restrictions). The response is then parsed and transformed into JSON Schema definition, where for each Digital Object type in openDS an individual JSON Schema definition is created. Figure 5 shows such a JSON Schema definition. These definitions can then be included in the processing service. An open task for the future is the implementation of an automated workflow which exports new definitions every time something has been changed in the Modelling Framework and pushes them to the processing service or to a registry of Schema definitions. However, a smart approach needs to be developed which makes use of versioned Schema definitions and takes into consideration that these changes can possibly invalidate existing data in the Digital Specimen repository.

```
{
  "$schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-04/schema",
  "$id": "http://sandbox.dissco.tech/schemas/0.1.0/2DImageObject",
  "type": "object",
  "required": [
    "mediaURL"
  ],
  "properties": {
    "mediaURL": {
      "type": "string"
    },
    "identifier": {
      "type": "string"
    },
    "mediaWidth": {
      "type": "integer"
    },
    "mediaHeight": {
      "type": "integer"
    }
  }
}
```

Figure 5: Example JSON Schema of the openDS Type 2DImageObject generated by the JSON Schema publishing script.

03 Outcome

Coverage of the First Version of the openDS

For the first version of the openDS, we decided to focus on several groups of classes that are mandatory for basic interoperability with the DiSSCo Technical Framework and that cover many of the use cases of the technical framework, in particular the Minimum Information about a Digital Specimen (MIDS, MIDS Task Group 2022) specification and the Specimen Data Refinery (SDR, Hardisty 2022). The core groups are: Digital Specimen, Multimedia, Agent, Provenance and Other.

Digital Specimen

This group currently only covers the single class of the Digital Specimen. It is the central concept of the specification. It has the most properties and links to all of the other classes. Later on, this group will also include the subtypes of the Digital Specimen, such as BotanySpecimen or AnthropologySpecimen. The properties of the Digital Specimen class were chosen and defined to align as closely as possible with the MIDS specification.

Multimedia

The Multimedia group includes the class DigitalRepresentation and all its subclasses. Besides the DigitalMediaObject and its subclasses for AudioObject, VideoObject, 2DImageObject and 3DImageObject, it also includes the class TextDescription.

Agent

This group describes entities that can interact with a specimen and it includes the abstract class Agent and its three subclasses Person, Organization and MachineAgent.

Provenance

This group comprises the foundational concepts to capture both retrospective provenance (detailed record or log of executed operations) and prospective provenance information (machine actionable recipe) based in particular on the EventProvenanceRecord and CreateUpdateDeleteEvent classes (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Tentative model in openDS to represent retrospective and prospective and provenance information based on the interplay of the openDS EventProvenanceRecord and CreateUpdateDeleteEvent classes. The detailed account of provenance information is based on a combination of the PROV ontology (PROV-O, Lebo 2013) for the record of the creation or processing context of data (provided by EventProvenanceRecord) and JSON-Patch (RFC6902, encapsulated in the CreateUpdateDeleteEvent) to provide machine actionable recipes (detailed in the upcoming DiSSCo Deliverable D6.4., Weiland et al. 2023).

Other

This group is for concepts that don't properly fit in the other groups mentioned above, but are not extensive enough to warrant the creation of another group. It contains the abstract class DigitalRepresentation which is the superclass for the class TextDescription, which is also part of this group and the aforementioned DigitalMediaObject.

Also in this group is the abstract class Collection with its two subclasses for PhysicalSpecimenCollection and DigitalSpecimenCollection. The PhysicalSpecimenCollection describes the collection where the physical specimen is located in its organisation, whereas the DigitalSpecimenCollection allows for grouping different digital specimens for all kinds of purposes, such as curated lists by collectors or taxonomic concepts.

URIs for Terms of openDS

Each term of openDS is identified with a unique URI. The URIs have the form

<https://terms.dissco.tech/terms/opends/<termName>>

and when resolved each URI will forward to a documentation of that term, like

<https://terms.dissco.tech/documentation/opends/#<termName>> .

The individual versions of a terms have URIs in the form

<https://terms.dissco.tech/terms/opends/versions/<termName>-<versionName>>

and when resolve to documentation URLs like

<https://terms.dissco.tech/documentation/opends/versions/#<termName>-<versionName>> .

Human Readable Documentation

The human readable documentation of the terms is accessible by resolving the URIs of the term (or its specific version) as detailed above. It will guide the reader in looking up the specific terms and their meanings. The documentation is available at <https://terms.dissco.tech/documentation/opens/>.

04 Outlook

Continuous Development

The specification outlined in this deliverable is only a first version of the Open Digital Specimen. Its development was focused on the core concepts for the compatibility with the DiSSCo Technical Framework. While this is a good first step, it also means that it is not a full specification that includes all of the elements that are expected from openDS. So further development of the schema is needed in the future to fully fit for all the expected future use cases.

MIDS Alignment

The openDS data model is defined to align as closely as possible to the specification of MIDS. Still, an explicit mapping of the openDS model to the MIDS elements will be required for the different subtypes of Digital Specimens, in particular for more complicated relations at higher MIDS levels, so that automated calculation of MIDS level for each specimen becomes possible. It will only be possible to finalize this work when the MIDS specification of all MIDS levels is completed.

Export as Ontology

In the initial phase of the working group activity there was the discussion about what kind of form openDS should have. The decision was made to have the primary technical form as a JSON Schema, as this fit better with the expected exchange formats and the overall technical infrastructure. The other prominent option was the export as an OWL (Web Ontology Language) ontology, though this would require a bit more work to make the specification compliant. However, with the setup of the DMF it is possible to export the data model both as a JSON Schema and an OWL ontology. So should at some future point the use cases of an export as an ontology arise, it would still be possible to generate it.

Content Negotiation

Currently, the term URIs only resolve to the human readable version of the documentation. A possible next step to full machine readability of the schema would be to add content negotiation to the resolver that delivers different results depending on the HTTP Accept header of the request. So if a machine tries to resolve the URI with the JSON Schema mime type (application/schema+json) as the content of the Accept header, the server should forward the machine to the JSON Schema files instead of the human readable documentation.

Further Automatization

While many of the steps required to export a new version are done via scripts and tools, the process still needs to be run by a human administrator and it requires several manual steps along the way. This could be reduced by further automating the steps and their coupling, thus allowing for quick releases of new versions of the specification.

Persistent Identifiers for Terms

As FAIR and FAIR Digital Object implementation is a key aspect for DiSSCo, it is important to understand how the DiSSCo Terms will be a FAIR component in the technical ecosystem. Identifying and linking the terminologies with different digital objects in a machine readable and actionable way thus would be beneficial towards the implementation of FAIR principles. In this regard, the use of Handle and DOI systems as the persistent identifier implementation provides a pathway forward. For more details, see Hardisty et al. 2021 where we looked into levels of scalability, community trust, persistence, governance, appropriateness of the scheme and suitability for future global adoption of a persistent identifier scheme for DiSSCo.

The following is one example of the best practices proposed and adopted in different research communities around the world that can provide some guidance:

F	Each vocabulary is denoted by a persistent unique web identifier Each term is denoted by a persistent unique web identifier It is possible to search for a term or vocabulary and get a web identifier for it The vocabulary is available from at least one repository recognised by the community
A	When the vocabulary or term identifier is de-referenced, a machine- or human-readable representation is returned, as requested
I	At least one representation conforms to a community standard for vocabularies The vocabulary includes mapping relations to other vocabularies
R	The license for use of the vocabulary is clear and accessible Enough metadata at vocabulary and term-level is provided, including provenance and maintenance information The definitions are sufficient for a user to understand what each term means

Figure 7: Summary of FAIR principles applied to a vocabulary from Cox et al 2021

Some of the questions we need to consider in the near future to drive our thinking and design work:

1. Should we consider the terms as another FAIR Digital Object?
2. If yes, then how do we specify and model these objects similar to the Digital Specimen objects?
3. If no, what is the rationale?
4. How do we align with other efforts such as the new extended GBIF data model (Robertson 2020), [TDWG](#), [gfbio](#) for instance?
5. What about other Research Infrastructures such as [eLTER](#) and [ICOS](#)? (to learn from their implementation and investigate interoperability issues?)

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